

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report of Chapter 5. Figure 5.24 *Spodoptera frugiperda* (fall armyworm) management practices used by Indigenous Peoples and local communities in Africa

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Project leader and contributors:

- Justice A. Tambo
- Patricia L. Howard

Description

This figure shows *Spodoptera frugiperda* (fall armyworm) management practices used by Indigenous Peoples and local communities in Africa.

Process overview

Cross-chapter literature review on indigenous peoples and local communities and invasive alien species (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5760266>) is used as a base database to filter the *Spodoptera frugiperda* (fall armyworm) management practices used by Indigenous Peoples and local communities in Africa.